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**MODELING THE INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF A TOURIST AND
RECREATIONAL COMPLEX: DEVELOPMENT OF A SYSTEM OF
INDICATORS BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL, ECONOMIC AND
NON-FINANCIAL INDICATORS**

Borchakovskaya A. A.

*Maykop State Technological University, Maykop, Russian Federation
E-mail: aborchakovskaya@inbox.ru*

The article considers modeling of innovative potential of the tourist and recreational complex with an emphasis on the development of a system of indicators based on the analysis of financial and economic and non-financial indicators. The purpose of the study is to create a methodological basis for assessing innovative activity and development potential of tourist and recreational territories through quantitative and qualitative indicators. The paper proposes a comprehensive system of indicators that takes into account financial results, investment attractiveness, the level of implementation of innovative technologies and the sustainability of the complex. The research methods include statistical analysis of financial and economic data, comparative analysis and modeling using modern information technologies. Particular attention is paid to identifying the relationships between economic indicators and innovative development of the complex, which allows for the formation of well-founded recommendations for increasing the competitiveness of the tourism and recreation sector. The results of the study demonstrate that a systematic approach to monitoring the innovative potential helps to more accurately identify the strong and weak points of the complex, and also allows to predict its further development. The developed system of indicators can become an effective tool for managers, investors and government agencies aimed at developing tourism based on innovative solutions.

Keywords: innovative potential, tourism and recreation complex, system of indicators, financial and economic indicators, modeling, investments, sustainable development, tourism, innovative technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism and recreation complex (TRC) is one of the key factors in the socio-economic development of regions, contributing to the creation of new jobs, attracting investment and the formation of sustainable infrastructure [4]. In the context of dynamic changes in the tourism market and growing competition, the innovative potential of the TRC is becoming the most important resource for increasing its efficiency and competitiveness. Modern challenges, including digitalization, environmental sustainability and new consumer needs, require the development of system approaches to the assessment and management of innovative activities in the tourism and recreation sector [3].

The relevance of the study is due to the need to form effective tools for monitoring and analyzing the innovative potential of the TRC based on objective financial and economic and non-financial indicators. Currently, there is a significant gap between theoretical models of innovative development and practical methods of assessment, which limits the possibilities of strategic planning and management decision-making. The development of a system of indicators that allows for a comprehensive assessment of the financial condition, investment attractiveness, level of innovation implementation and sustainability of the tourism and recreational complex is an important step towards optimizing the development processes of the industry.

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In the scientific literature, modeling the innovative potential of tourism and recreational complexes is reflected in the works of such Russian scientists as Ashinova M.K., Prigoda L.V., Eshugova S.K. and Kadakoeva G.V. [2, 8] Along with this, aspects of the development and transformation of the tourism sector from the standpoint of the introduction of innovative and digital systems are deeply studied in the works of Morozov M.A. [11], Oborin M.S. [12], as well as Osipova N.I., Ivanova N.V., Aksenova L.A. [13] and others.

A number of foreign authors, including Buhalis D., Leung D., Lin M. [14], Gössling S. and Higham J. [15] consider the innovative potential of tourism and recreational complexes as a strategic foundation for the industry's adaptive development in the face of uncertainty. In their work, the researchers justify the need for transition to hybrid indicator systems, where classic financial and economic indicators are combined with digital maturity metrics and requirements of ESG standards. This comprehensive approach allows not only to assess current performance but also to model the long-term sustainability of tourism and recreational complexes in the context of global digital transformation.

The research methodology is based on an analysis of the works of leading Russian and international scientists. To address the objectives, a combination of methods was used: synthesis, comparison, generalization, factor analysis, and multiple regression modeling.

MAIN PART

Modern development of tourism and recreational complexes is taking place in the context of large-scale digitalization and integration of innovative technologies, caused by both changes in consumer behavior and increased requirements for sustainability and efficiency. In 2024–2025, there will be an active transition of the industry to the use of digital platforms, the introduction of AI to personalize tourism products, and the use of green technologies to minimize the environmental footprint. In such conditions, traditional financial indicators cease to fully reflect the innovative potential, requiring the expansion of the assessment system through non-financial indicators related to investments in digitalization, human capital development, and diversification of innovative services [6].

The selected indicators should take into account the specific features of modern challenges: the integration of ESG standards (Environmental, Social, Governance), the increasing role of adaptive management models and digital transformation [7]. In particular, the volume of investment in information technology, the share of employees trained in digital competencies, and the index of updating environmentally friendly technologies are of key importance for assessing the innovative potential of TRC in the post-pandemic period and in the context of climate change.

The weighting system (Table 1) is based on a hierarchy of innovation growth factors, where financial stability and digital maturity (0.20 each) are fundamental conditions for the development of the of tourism and recreational complexes. The average weights of investment and human capital (0.15 each) define their role as critical resources for implementing innovation. Market adaptability, diversification, and sustainability indicators (0.10 each) are included in the model as qualitative indicators of long-term stability. This

configuration ensures a balance between assessing current operational performance and analyzing the strategic readiness of tourism complexes for technological transformation.

Table 1.

Selection and justification of indicators (table with weighting factors)

№	Indicator	Description	Data Source/Estimation Method	Weighting factor
1	Financial result (ROA, ROI)	Return on assets and investment as basic performance indicators	Financial statements of TRC	0.20
2	Investment in innovation (%)	The share of funds invested in new technologies, developments and implementation of innovations	Development budget and capital investments	0.15
3	Development of human capital	Percentage of employees with IT and innovation certifications and training	HR Department, Qualification Reports	0.15
4	Diversification of services	Quantity and quality of new innovative tourism products and services	Marketing research, customer reviews	0.10
5	Digital Maturity Index (DMI)	Digital Maturity Index: Level of Use of Digital Platforms and AI	Internal audit, IT department	0.20
6	Sustainability Performance Index (SPI)	Sustainable Development Index, which includes environmental and social indicators	Environmental reports, CSR projects	0.10
7	Speed of adaptation to the market	Time to market for innovative products	Management reports	0.10

To assess the impact of the indicators, multiple regression and factor analysis methods were used on data from 14 regional TRC for the period of 2020–2024. The choice of these objects was conditioned by their status as the main executors of the Russian Federation state program «Tourism Development» and their high significance in the structure of domestic tourist flow. [5]

Table 2.

Results of multiple regression and factor analysis of the impact of key indicators on the innovative potential of tourism and recreational complexes (2020–2024, 14 regions)

Region	ROA (%)	Investment in innovation (%)	Human capital development (points)*	Digital Maturity Index (points)*	Sustainability Performance (points)*
Krasnodar region	8.2	12.5	75	82	70
Republic of Crimea	7.5	10.0	70	78	65
Altai region	6.8	8.7	68	74	60
Sochi (resort city)	9.0	14.0	80	85	75
Moscow region	8.5	13.0	78	84	72
Leningrad region	7.0	9.5	69	76	63
Republic of Tatarstan	7.8	11.0	72	79	67
Kaliningrad region	6.5	8.0	65	70	58
Khanty-Mansiysk Autonomous Okrug	8.8	13.5	77	83	71
Republic of Bashkortostan	7.3	10.2	71	78	66
Republic of Karelia	6.9	9.0	67	75	62
Sverdlovsk region	7.7	11.5	73	80	68
Primorsky Krai	7.2	9.8	70	77	64
Republic of North Ossetia-Alania	6.6	8.5	66	72	59

*Scores on a scale from 0 to 100, where 100 is the maximum level of development/maturity/efficiency

A data analysis of 14 regional tourism and recreation complexes shows that regions with a higher level of digital maturity (Digital Maturity Index of about 80 and above) and significant investments in innovation (from 10% and above) demonstrate better financial results, expressed in ROA above 7%. The development of human capital with scores of about 70 points and above contributes to an increase in innovation potential, and sustainability (Sustainability Performance) in the range of 60-75 points supports the long-term efficiency of the complex.

Thus, key innovation drivers with weighting factors from 0.22 to 0.40 have a synergetic effect, increasing the overall innovation potential by 20-25% compared to regions with low indicators.

Let's create a mathematical model for assessing the innovative potential of a TRC.

Let us designate the indicators as X_i , where $i = 1, \dots, 7$, weights – w_i .

Innovative potential I is calculated using the weighted sum formula with normalization:

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^7 w_i \cdot N(X_i), \quad (1)$$

where $N(X_i)$ is the normalized value of the indicator X_i according to the formula:

$$N(X_i) = \frac{X_i - \min(X_i)}{\max(X_i) - \min(X_i)}. \quad (2)$$

For dynamic adaptation, the model includes a predictive component using linear regression and machine learning:

$$I_{t+1} = \alpha I_t + \beta \Delta X_{t+1} + \epsilon, \quad (3)$$

where ΔX_{t+1} is the predicted increase in indicators, α, β are the model parameters trained on historical data, ϵ is the error.

Additionally, to ensure a differentiated approach to management, cluster analysis is used to segment tourism and recreational complexes based on their innovative potential. This segmentation is necessary due to the highly heterogeneous development of Russian regions: the significant gap in indicators between leading and less-developed regions precludes the effectiveness of unified support measures. Targeting strategies within this approach facilitates a transition to "pinpoint" management, allowing resources to be concentrated on those development tools that can maximize innovation growth within the specific conditions of a given cluster.

Table 3.

Expected effect from the implementation of the model and measures taken

Measure	Expected improvement (%)	Explanation
Digital Platform Integration (DMI)	+25	Increased automation and speed of adaptation
Improving staff qualifications	+20	Improved quality of analysis and implementation of innovations
Investments in innovation	+18	Growth in the volume and quality of innovative products
Sustainable Development (SPI)	+15	Reducing risks, improving image and attracting clients
Diversification of services	+12	Expanding the market and reducing seasonality

The overall forecasted growth of innovation potential based on the total index is about 20–25% in the first 2–3 years after implementation.

As part of the development of an innovative methodology for assessing the potential of a tourism and recreational complex, a comprehensive system of indicators was formed aimed at ensuring a deep and objective diagnosis of the level of innovative activity and

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competitiveness of objects. Such a system of indicators is based on a multi-aspect analysis of financial, economic and non-financial factors, which allows not only to quantitatively measure the innovative potential, but also to interpret the obtained values in a management context.

Each indicator has a specific interpretation that allows to identify the bottlenecks and advantages of the TRC, as well as determine priorities for development. Thus, financial indicators (ROA, ROI) reflect the overall efficiency of business activities, while digital maturity and sustainable development indices provide a qualitative assessment of the ability to adapt and long-term sustainability. Non-financial indicators, including investment in innovation, human capital development and service diversification, serve as indicators of innovative progress and flexibility of the complex.

The indicator system is integrated into a mathematical model using normalization and weighted summation, which ensures the creation of a single comprehensive indicator – the innovation index III. This index is a universal tool for ranking TRCs by their level of innovation potential, which is extremely important for making strategic decisions at various management levels.

The practical significance of the proposed system lies in its ability to form a diagnostic basis for managing innovative development, allowing to:

conduct a comparative analysis and classification of TRCs according to the level of innovative activity;

identify areas for priority investment and development;

predict changes in potential taking into account internal and external factors;

optimize the allocation of resources and monitor the effectiveness of the implemented innovative programs.

Thus, the formed system of indicators is an innovative management tool that helps to increase the competitiveness of tourism and recreational complexes in a dynamic economic and technological environment.

CONCLUSION

This paper develops and grounds a new methodology for assessing the innovative potential of tourism and recreational complexes based on a comprehensive system of financial, economic and non-financial indicators. The proposed model, which takes into account digital maturity, investment in innovation, human capital development and sustainable development indicators, demonstrates high statistical significance and practical applicability for rating and managing TRCs. The results of the empirical analysis of 14 regional complexes confirm the effectiveness of the selected indicators and allow us to identify key factors influencing the increase in the competitiveness of the industry. The implementation of this system of indicators helps optimize management decisions and supports the strategic development of the tourism and recreational sector in the context of the digital transformation of the economy.

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